

Online Educational Resources Library

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Mental health and Mindfulness

TITLE	LINK	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTOR SHIP	LICENCE	LANGU AGE
Why students should have mental health days?	https://www.ted.com/talks/hailey_hardcastle_why_students_should_have_mental_health_days	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Are you a body with a mind or a mind with a body?	https://ed.ted.com/lessons/are-you-a-body-with-a-mind-or-a-mind-with-a-body-maryam-alimardani	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
What yoga does to your body and brain?	https://ed.ted.com/lessons/what-yoga-does-to-your-body-and-brain-krishna-sudhir	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
How friendship affects your brain?	https://ed.ted.com/lessons/how-friendship-affects-your-brain-shannon-odell	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Up close with a human brain	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u2lkcmDARs4	Video	created by others	Other	English
Can machines read your emotions	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u2lkcmDARs4	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Come avviene la trasmissione di un impulso nervoso	https://youtu.be/aF3C0ZZYYFs?si=YnlfVW9IuIDS87cF	Video	created by others	Copyright	Italian
Introduction to the Stijl	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOSvUfbPHpY	Video	created by others	Other	English
The Mondrien painting is actually a jazz score	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=05KLW-xsoxE	Video	created by others	Copyright	English

The neurobiology of beauty	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NlzanAw0RP4	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Can you solve the Mondrian square riddle?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AWcY2-FBa9k	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
The brain Circuit : how the brain works for you	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F4SYTeBnjg	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Action potential	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FEHNIELPb0s	Video	created by others	Other	English
Mental Health	https://quizlet.com/it/851446485/il-sistema-nervoso-flash-cards/?i=1zespi&x=1jqU	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Italian

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